

EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF TEACHERS' SELF-EFFICACY BELIEFS ON TEACHERS' PSYCHOLOGICAL RESILIENCE LEVELS

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to examine the effects of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs on teachers' psychological resilience levels. In this quantitative study, correlational survey model was used. The research group of this study consisted of 189 teachers, 108 (57.1%) female and 81 (42.9%) male working in private and state institutions in Karatay, Meram and Selçuklu districts of Konya. In order to collect data in the study, Personal Information Form, Teacher Self-Efficacy Belief Scale, and a Short Psychological Resilience Scale were used. SPSS 23.0 package program was used for the analysis of the data collected in the research. According to the results of the research, teachers' self-efficacy beliefs differed significantly according to the perceived parental attitude during the upbringing period. Teachers' psychological resilience levels did not differ significantly according to the perceived parental attitudes during upbringing. It was found that

teachers' self-efficacy beliefs explained 18.6% of the variance in teachers' psychological resilience levels.

Keywords: self-efficacy, teachers' self-efficacy, psychological resilience, education science, teachers' psychological resilience

Introduction

Education forms the basis of the steps towards the development of individuals and societies and includes more than one element. Teachers are at the forefront of these elements. The progress of the educational process in a beneficial and desired direction is directly proportional to the efforts of teachers. In order for teachers to be able to direct the education process correctly, their psychological resilience levels should be high. As teachers' psychological resilience levels and self-efficacy beliefs increase, their efforts to improve the quality of education also increase. Today, individuals are faced with different living conditions and the difficulties that come with them. In the face of these challenging conditions, individuals' psychological resilience is affected and their energy required for the continuation of life is depleted. In order to gain this necessary energy, the individual designs the self and living conditions that he/she wants to be in his/her mind. The imagined and desired self guides teachers to show success and effort. They apply to the ideal self in order to cope with the difficult situations they encounter in the school environment. When they can cope with difficult situations, there is an increase in self-confidence, otherwise there is an increase in stress (Besler, 2006).

Teachers have a great place in our society. Many factors affect the performance of teachers who raise new generations and shape the future. The most important of these factors are psychological resilience and self-efficacy.

Teaching is a profession that requires direct communication with students. It is one of the most important elements of education and training life. The ability to carry out education and training in a healthy way and to make it more qualified is a situation related to teachers. Teachers are role models with their behaviour, personality traits and stance. Considering these factors and the working conditions of teachers, the teaching profession becomes stressful. In the face of negative situations, while some teachers adapt to new situations, some teachers have difficulty in adapting or cannot adapt (Özbağır, 2019). It can be said that teachers' burnout levels may increase due to low adaptability and psychological resilience.

Teachers, like other people, face many difficulties throughout their life periods and experience many changes due to these difficulties. While some people can adapt quickly to these changes, some people may give up in the face of these difficulties. This situation shows that various characteristics of people facilitate their adaptation processes.

The process of recovery from negative experiences that individuals face in life and their power to adapt to their normal lives are explained by the concept of psychological health (Stewart, Ride, & Mangham, 1997). In the literature, the concept of psychological resilience is considered as a personality trait. While Garnezy (1991) shows the concept of psychological resilience as a personality trait of children in risky environments; Connor and Davidson (2003) express it as personality traits that enable the individual to strive against risky situations. People with high psychological resilience exhibit the behaviour of making efforts, sustaining life and developing and prevailing in the face of challenging situations (Eminağaoğlu, 2006).

The concept of psychological resilience, which is one of the concepts of positive psychology and has started to take place in the national literature, has

been explained by researchers by referring to different fields. According to Lazarus (1993), the concept of psychological resilience is defined by comparisons made on the physical states of metal in the process of hardness, fragility, softness and flexibility. It is seen that researches have started to be conducted in Turkey since 2000s regarding the concept which is tried to be defined in the field of behavioural psychology (Gizir, 2004). There are many factors affecting the level of psychological resilience.

Protective and risk factors are the most important of these factors. Protective factors are the factors that facilitate the individual to give constructive reactions in order to reduce the negative effects of risk factors and facilitate adaptation (Karairmak, 2006). Individuals with protective factors have features such as reducing the effect of stress in dangerous or distressing situations, protecting self-confidence and self-esteem positively, controlling emotional state, etc. (Özer, 2013). Another factor affecting psychological resilience is risk factors. Situations or behaviours that increase the likelihood of a person developing a certain physical or mental illness are risk factors (Şahin, 2014). Risk factors may differ in individuals. Gizir (2007) thinks that the difference in risk factors in individuals is due to individual, familial and environmental factors. When the literature is examined, one of the concepts closely related to the concept of psychological resilience is self-efficacy (Doğan, 2020). Self-efficacy is an individual's belief in his/her own abilities and efforts to do a job. According to Bandura (1997), the concept of self-efficacy is defined as a person's perception of his/her ability to evaluate his/her own skills and abilities and to transform them into behaviour. According to Bıkmaz (2004), self-efficacy is people's approach to various situations and their beliefs about their ability to cope with situations such as work stress. Teacher self-efficacy is defined as self-confidence in one's own ability to help, motivate and influence students in the learning process (Moe,

et al., 2010). Teachers with high self-efficacy beliefs establish positive relationships with their students, take responsibility for student success, and use different methods and materials. In addition, teachers with high self-efficacy beliefs are more willing to implement new programmes and approaches, more patient towards students with learning difficulties and more combative in the face of challenging situations (Podell & Soodak, 1993).

The concepts of self-efficacy and psychological resilience occupy an important place in the lives of individuals. While individuals' belief in a job is determined by their self-efficacy beliefs, their continuity and performance are closely related to their psychological resilience levels.

Although the concepts of psychological resilience and self-efficacy are important in all professional groups, they are more prominent in the teaching profession. Teachers with high self-efficacy beliefs also have high beliefs that they can overcome and overcome difficulties, and this situation also affects the level of psychological resilience. In this study, in which teachers' self-efficacy beliefs and the effect of these beliefs on the level of psychological resilience are examined, the question "What is the effect of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs on their level of psychological resilience?" was sought to be answered. An answer to the question was sought.

Sub-problems of the research

1. Do teachers' self-efficacy beliefs differ significantly according to the parental attitude perceived while being raised?
2. Do teachers' psychological resilience levels differ significantly according to the parental attitude perceived during upbringing?
3. Do teachers' self-efficacy beliefs predict their psychological resilience levels in a significant way? It is in the form.

2. Research Design

This study, in which the effect of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs on psychological resilience is examined, is in the relational research model, one of the general survey models. This research model is conducted to determine the relationships between two or more variables and to obtain clues about cause and effect (Büyüköztürk, Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz, Demirel, 2014).

3. Study Group

The study group of this research consists of teachers working at different levels in private and public schools in the central districts of Konya province in the 2022-2023 academic year. In this research, Karatay, Meram and Selçuklu districts were selected due to their easy accessibility. 189 teachers participated in the research. Parental attitudes were stated as democratic by 77 teachers (40.8%), indifferent-careless by 27 teachers (14.2%), oppressive-authoritarian by 59 teachers (31.2%), and perfectionist by 26 teachers (13.8%).

4. Measures

Teacher Self-Efficacy Belief Scale

The Teaching Self-Efficacy Belief Scale was developed by Çolak, Yorulmaz, and Altinkurt in 2017. The literature on self-efficacy was reviewed and items were created. The research group for the scale consisted of teachers working in Muğla province in 2016-2017. The 27-item scale consists of four sub-dimensions: 'Academic Self-Efficacy', 'Social Self-Efficacy', 'Intellectual Self-Efficacy' and 'Professional Self-Efficacy'. There are five items in the 'Academic Self-Efficacy' factor, seven items in the 'Professional Self-Efficacy' factor, eight items in the 'Social Self-Efficacy' factor and seven items in the 'Intellectual Self-Efficacy' factor. High scores from the whole scale or its sub-dimensions indicate that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs are high. In addition, Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency coefficient was analysed for the reliability of the scale. This

coefficient was calculated as .75 for Academic Self-Efficacy factor, .86 for Professional Self-Efficacy factor, .88 for Social Self-Efficacy factor, .87 for Intellectual Self-Efficacy and .95 for the whole scale. The calculated internal consistency coefficients show that the reliability of the scale is high (Çolak, Yorulmaz, & Altinkurt, 2017). In this study, Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency coefficient of the Teacher Self-Efficacy Belief Scale was calculated again to test the reliability of the scale and it was found to be .94.

Short Psychological Resilience Scale

The English form of the Brief Psychological Resilience Scale (BSRS) used in the study was developed by Smith et al. (2008) to measure the psychological resilience levels of individuals. The adaptation of this scale into Turkish and its validity and reliability studies were conducted by Doğan (2015) with 295 university students. The scale is a 5-point Likert-type scale with 6 items. A high score in the scale indicates a high level of psychological resilience. The test-retest reliability coefficient of the scale was calculated between .62 and .69. The internal consistency coefficient of the Turkish version of the scale was found to be .83, while the internal consistency reliability coefficient was found between .80 and .91. In this study, Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency coefficient of the Brief Psychological Resilience Scale was calculated again to test the reliability of the scale and it was found to be .88.

5. Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were calculated for all variables and the aim of the study was to reveal the effect of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs on their psychological resilience levels. 189 teachers participated in the study. The data collected in the study were analysed using SPSS 23.0 package programme. After the data were collected by applying measurement tools to the participants, these data were transferred to the computer environment and made suitable for

analyses. The independent variable of this research is teachers' self-efficacy beliefs and the dependent variable is their psychological resilience.

When the skewness and kurtosis coefficients of the data obtained from the teachers were examined, it was seen that they were within $\pm 1,5$ value range. Assuming that the data were normally distributed, parametric tests were used. One-way ANOVA test was conducted to determine whether the scores of the teachers obtained from the Teacher Self-Efficacy Beliefs Scale and the Brief Psychological Resilience Scale differed significantly according to the perceived parental attitude while being raised. Simple Linear Regression Analysis technique was used to determine whether teachers' self-efficacy beliefs predicted psychological resilience at a significant level.

6. Results

In this part of the study, the findings obtained from the research questions are given.

The first sub-problem of the study is "Do teachers' self-efficacy beliefs differ significantly according to the parental attitude perceived while being raised?". The findings related to whether teachers' self-efficacy beliefs differ significantly according to the parental attitude perceived during upbringing are presented in Table 1.

When Table 1 is examined, teachers' self-efficacy beliefs show a significant difference ($p < .05$) according to the variable of parental attitude perceived during upbringing. In order to determine the source of the difference between the groups, Tukey analysis from Post-Hoc tests was applied. Significant differences were observed between the self-efficacy beliefs of teachers who perceived their parental attitudes as oppressive-authoritarian and the self-efficacy beliefs of teachers who perceived their parental attitudes as perfectionist. The mean scores of self-efficacy beliefs of teachers who perceived their parental

attitudes as perfectionist (\bar{x} =4.260) were significantly higher than the mean scores of self-efficacy beliefs of teachers who perceived their parental attitudes as oppressive-authoritarian (\bar{x} =3.970).

Table 1

One-Way ANOVA and Post-Hoc Results of Teachers' Self-Efficacy Beliefs According to Perceived Parental Attitudes While Growing Up

Scale	Parentel Attitude	N	\bar{x}	Ss	F	P	Difference
Teacher Self-Efficacy Beliefs Scale	A: Democratic	77	4.106	.442	2.834	.04*	C-D
	B: Disinterested-Uncaring	27	3.983	.503			
	C: Oppressive-Authority	59	3.970	.470			
	D: Perfectionist	26	4.260	.472			

*p<.05

The second sub-problem of the study is "Do the psychological resilience levels of teachers differ significantly according to the parental attitude perceived while being raised?". The findings regarding whether the psychological resilience levels of teachers differ significantly according to the parental attitude perceived during upbringing are presented in Table 2.

One-way ANOVA test was conducted to determine whether teachers' scores on the brief psychological resilience scale differed significantly according to the variable of parental attitude perceived during upbringing. As a result of the analyses, the psychological resilience scores of the teachers were ranked as follows: teachers perceiving parental attitude as democratic (\bar{x} =3.480), teachers perceiving parental attitude as perfectionist (\bar{x} =3.307), teachers perceiving parental attitude as indifferent-careless (\bar{x} =3.290) and teachers perceiving

parental attitude as oppressive-authoritarian (\bar{x} =3.257). When the analyses were examined, it was seen that the difference was not significant ($p>.05$).

Table 2

One-Way ANOVA and Post-Hoc Results of Teachers' Psychological Resilience Levels According to Perceived Parental Attitude While Growing Up

Scale	Parentel Attitude	N	\bar{x}	Ss	F	P	Difference
Short Psychological Resilience Scale		77	3.480	.751	1.140	.334*	Absent
	A: Democratic	27	3.290	.761			
	B: Disinterested-Uncaring	59	3.257	.726			
	C: Oppressive-Authority	26	3.307	.816			
	D: Perfectionist						

* $p<.05$

The third sub-problem of the study is "Do teachers' self-efficacy beliefs predict their psychological resilience levels in a significant way?". The findings regarding the role of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in predicting their psychological resilience levels are presented in Table 3.

Simple linear regression analysis was performed to determine the effect of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs on their psychological resilience levels. As a result of the analyses, the regression model was found to be significant ($F(1-187)=42.766$, $p<.005$). Teachers' self-efficacy beliefs explained 18.6% of the variance related to psychological resilience ($R^2=.186$). It can be said that as teachers' self-efficacy beliefs increase, their psychological resilience levels will also increase.

According to the regression analysis results, the regression equation predicting teachers' psychological resilience levels is as follows:

Teachers' Psychological Resilience Levels = (0.691 X Teachers' Self-Efficacy Beliefs Score) + 0.548.

It was determined that a one-unit increase in teachers' self-efficacy beliefs score would cause a 0.691-unit increase in teachers' psychological resilience levels

Table 3

Simple Linear Regression Analysis Results Regarding the Role of Teachers' Self-Efficacy Beliefs in Predicting Psychological Resilience Levels

Predicted Variable	Predictor Variable	B	Ss	Beta	T	P
Short Psychological Resilience Scale	Constant	.548	.433		1.266	.207
	Teachers' Self-Efficacy Beliefs	.691	.106	.431	6.540	.000

R=.431, R²=.186, F₍₁₋₁₈₇₎=42.766, p=.000

7. Discussion

The findings regarding whether teachers' self-efficacy beliefs differed significantly according to the parental attitude perceived during upbringing were discussed in the light of the information in the literature.

It was seen that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs differed significantly according to the parental attitude perceived during upbringing. When the findings obtained in the study were analysed, it was seen that the mean scores of self-efficacy beliefs of teachers who perceived their parental attitudes as perfectionist were higher than those of teachers who perceived their parental attitudes as oppressive-authoritarian. When the literature was analysed, no research supporting this study was found. Individuals who perceive parental attitudes as

perfectionist take on various tasks and responsibilities in order to make their parents happy. They devote themselves to continuous self-improvement in order to do this task in the best way. The difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs can be evaluated in this context.

The findings regarding whether the psychological resilience levels of teachers vary significantly according to the perceived parental attitude during upbringing were discussed in the light of the information in the literature.

When it was examined whether the psychological resilience levels of the teachers differed significantly according to the perceived parental attitude during upbringing, no significant difference was found.

When the literature is examined, there are many studies supporting this research. In the studies conducted by Arslan, 2018; Dilmaç & Pınar, 2020, it was observed that the psychological resilience levels of the participants did not differ significantly according to the perceived parental attitude. In the study conducted by Hoşoğlu et al. (2020), it was observed that there was no significant difference in the psychological resilience levels of prospective teachers according to the perceived parental attitude. A similar study was conducted by Kaçar (2022). In this study, there was no significant difference in the psychological resilience levels of teachers according to perceived parental attitude.

In this study conducted to determine whether teachers' self-efficacy beliefs predict their psychological resilience levels, self-efficacy beliefs explained 18.6% of the variance related to psychological resilience. As a result of this finding, it can be interpreted that teachers' high competence in their professional duties and responsibilities can undertake a protective function for their psychological resilience in the face of challenging situations.

When the literature is analysed, similar studies to the findings of this research are found. In the study conducted by Terzi (2008), it was concluded that

self-efficacy predicts psychological resilience. In the study conducted by Dural (2018), a positive and significant relationship was found between psychological resilience and general self-efficacy perception. In the study conducted by Atak (2018), a positive and significant relationship was found between psychological resilience and self-efficacy.

8. Conclusion & Suggestions

As a result of the findings and results obtained from the research, the following recommendations presented:

- Teachers can be directed to family counselling to increase their self-efficacy beliefs about parental attitudes and psychological resilience levels.
- Family activities and seminars can be organised to reduce the negative effects of parental attitudes.
- In-service trainings can be organised by MoNE to increase teachers' self-efficacy beliefs and thus their psychological resilience.
- This study was conducted on teachers. The relationship between self-efficacy beliefs and psychological resilience can be examined in different occupational groups.
- Different study groups and variables can be preferred in future studies with the variables in this study.

9. Ethic

In this study, the ethics committee approval was obtained from Necmettin Erbakan University Social and Human Sciences Research and Publication Ethics Board of Necmettin Erbakan University at its meeting dated 16.04.2021 and numbered 04 with the decision number 2021/209.

References

- Arslan, H. (2018). Psikolojik danışmanların mutluluk, psikolojik sağlamlık ve bağımlılık durumları arasındaki ilişkiler [Relationships between psychological counsellors' happiness, psychological resilience and dependency] . *Sağlık Bilimlerinde Eğitim Dergisi*, 1(1), 17-35.
- Atak, T. (2018). *Demanslı hastalarla ilgilenen aile üyelerinin bakım veren yükünün incelenmesi* [Investigation of caregiver burden of family members caring for patients with dementia] (Master's thesis, Ege University, İzmir, Turkey).
- Bandura, A. (1997). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, 84(2), 191-215.
- Besler, E. (2006). *Mesleki ve teknik eğitim kurumlarında görev yapan öğretmenlerde tükenmişliğin incelenmesi* [Investigation of burnout in teachers working in vocational and technical education institutions] (Master's thesis, Marmara University, İstanbul, Turkey).
- Bıkmaz, F. H. (2004). Sınıf öğretmenlerinin fen öğretiminde öz-yeterlik inancı ölçeğinin geçerlik ve güvenilirlik çalışması [Validity and reliability study of classroom teachers' self-efficacy belief scale in science teaching]. *Milli Eğitim Dergisi*, 161-199.
- Büyüköztürk, Ş., Çakmak, E., Akgün, Ö., Karadeniz, Ş., & Demirel, F. (2014). *Bilimsel araştırma yöntemleri* [Scientific research methods]. (17. Baskı). Ankara, Turkey: Ayrıntı.
- Connor, K. M., & Davidson, J.R. (2003). Development of a new resilience scale: The connor davidson resilience scale (CD-RISC). *Depression And Anxiety*, 18, 76-82.
- Çolak, İ., Yorulmaz, Y., & Altinkurt, Y. (2017). Öğretmen özyeterlik inancı ölçeği geçerlik ve güvenilirlik çalışması [Teacher self-efficacy belief scale validity and reliability study]. *Muğla Sıtkı Koçman Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 4(1), 20-32.
- Dılmaç, B., & Pınar, Ş. (2020). *Hemşirelik öğrencilerinin psikolojik sağlamlık ve öz-şefkat düzeylerinin belirlenmesi* [Determination of psychological resilience and self-compassion levels of nursing students] (Master's thesis, Necmettin Erbakan University, Konya, Turkey).

- Dođan, B. B. (2020). *Okul psikolojik danıřmanlarının (rehber öğretmenlerinin) psikolojik sađlamlık, özyeterlik ve iř doyumunu arasındaki iliřkinin incelenmesi* [Investigation of the relationship between psychological resilience, self-efficacy and job satisfaction of school counsellors (guidance counsellors)] (Master's thesis, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, Turkey).
- Dođan, T. (2015). Kısa psikolojik sađlamlık ölçeđi'nin türkçe uyarlaması: Geçerlik ve güvenilirlik çalıřması [Turkish adaptation of the short psychological resilience scale: Validity and reliability study]. *The Journal of Happiness and Well-Being*, 3(1), 93-102.
- Dural, F. Z. (2018). *Yař arası yetiřkinliklerde psikolojik dayanıklılıđın öz yeterlilik üzerindeki etkisi* [The effect of psychological resilience on self-efficacy in age-intermediate adulthood] (Master's thesis, Üsküdar University, İstanbul, Turkey).
- Eminađaođlu, N. (2006). *Güç kořullarda yařayan sokak çocuklarda dayanıklılık (sađlamlık)* [Resilience in street children living in difficult conditions (robustness)] (Yayımlanmamıř Doktora Tezi). Ege Üniversitesi, Eđitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İzmir.
- Garnezy, N. (1991). Resilience in children's adaptation to negative life events and stressed environments. *Pediatric Annals*, 20, 459-466.
- Gizir, C. A. (2004). *Akademik sađlamlık: yoksulluk içindeki sekizinci sınıf öğrencilerin akademik başarılarına katkıda bulunan koruyucu faktörlerin incelenmesi* [Academic resilience: an examination of protective factors that contribute to the academic achievement of eighth-grade students in poverty] (Doctoral dissertation, Middle East Technical University, Ankara, Turkey).
- Gizir, C. A. (2007). Psikolojik sađlamlık, risk faktörleri ve koruyucu faktörler üzerinde bir derleme çalıřması [A review study on psychological resilience, risk factor and protective factors]. *Türk Psikolojik Danıřma ve Rehberlik Dergisi*, 3(28), 113-128.
- Hořođlu, R., Kodaz, A. F., Bingöl, T. Y., & Batık, M. V. (2018). Öğretmen adaylarında psikolojik sađlamlık [Psychological resilience in pre-service teachers]. *OPUS Uluslararası Toplum Arařtırmaları Dergisi*, 8(14), 217-239.

- Kaçar, T. (2022). *Öğretmenlerin psikolojik sağlamlıkları, yaşam becerileri ve öz-kontrolleri arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi* [Examining the relationship between teachers' psychological resilience, life skills and self-control] (Master's thesis, Necmettin Erbakan University, Konya, Turkey).
- Kararımk, Ö. (2006). Psikolojik sağlamlık, risk faktörleri ve koruyucu faktörler [Psychological resilience, risk factors and protective factors]. *Türk Psikolojik Danışma ve Rehberlik Dergisi*, 3(26), 129-142.
- Lazarus, R. S. (1993). From psychological stress to emotions: A history of changing outlooks. *Annual Review Of Psychology*, 44, 1-21.
- Moe, A., Pazzaglia, F., & Ronconi, L. (2010). When being able is not enough: the combined value of positive affect and self-efficacy for job satisfaction in teaching. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 26(5), 1145–1153.
- Özbağır, T. (2019). *Öğretmenlerde psikolojik dayanıklılığının duygusal zekayla pozitif öğretmen özellikleriyle ve demografik değişkenlerle ilişkisi* [The relationship between psychological resilience in teachers and emotional intelligence, positive teacher characteristics and demographic variables] (Master's thesis, Yıldız Teknik University, İstanbul, Turkey).
- Özer, E. (2013). *Üniversite öğrencilerinin psikolojik sağlamlık düzeylerinin duygusal zeka ve beş faktör kişilik özellikleri açısından incelenmesi* [Investigation of psychological resilience levels of university students in terms of emotional intelligence and five factor personality traits] (Doctoral dissertation, Necmettin Erbakan University, Konya, Turkey).
- Podell, D., & Soodak, L. (1993). Teacher efficacy and bias in special education referral. *Journal of Educational Research*, 86, 247-253.
- Smith, J. L., & Hollinger-Smith, L. (2008). Savoring, resilience, and psychological well-being in older adults. *Aging Ment Health*, 19(3), 192-200.
- Stewart, M., Ride, G. J., & Mangham, C. (1997). Fostering children's resilience . *Journal Of Pediatric Nursing*, 12(1), 21-31.
- Şahin, D. (2014). *Öğretmenlerin özduyarlılıklarının psikolojik sağlamlık ve yaşam doyumu açısından incelenmesi* [Investigation of teachers' self-compassion in terms of psychological resilience and life satisfaction] (Master's thesis, Karadeniz Teknik University, Trabzon, Turkey).

Terzi, Ő. (2008). Őniversite ğrencilerinin kendini toparlama gcnn isel koruyucu faktrlerle iliŐkisi [The relationship between university students' self-recovery power and intrinsic protective factors]. *Hacettepe Őniversitesi Eėitim Fakltesi Dergisi*, 35, 297-306.

Acknowledgements

This article is derived from Master's thesis entitled "Examining The Impact of Teachers' Self-Efficacy Beliefs on Psychological Resilience Levels" written by Sevim Rahime Temiz under the supervision of Prof. Dr. mer Beyhan.